

Women Empowerment

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Abstract

The woman is the real shape of the future in the sense that she guides the younger generation besides this maternal duty, women have a very important role in society. Indian women belong to all sections of society and are engaged in multifarious tasks. They carry too many responsibilities like running the new generations and braving the difficulties arising from spiralling prices. Empowering women is very much important nowadays.

Women empowerment is a process that helps the women to realize their identity and capacity. It enables them to have access to resources, greater stay in decision making, more ability to plan their time, responsibility to free from irrelevant customs, traditions and practices and prejudices and gain self confidence. (Singh, p.31)

Keywords: Gender equality, economic empowerment, welfare, access of opportunities.

Introduction:

Need of women empowerment:

Empowerment of women is essential all over the world. It is important to ensure equality and to end exploitation and discrimination from society, to develop self-esteem and confidence, to realize their potential and enhance their collective bargaining power. It aware women of their status, rights and opportunities towards ensuring gender equality.

Empowering women ensure development of skill to manage all digitalization. It ensures greater participation in the decision making process for the women in all institutions. Women's empowerment is essential for many reasons, such as gender equality. The women's empowerment is the major part of achieving the gender equity goal in sustainable development. Without empowering women we cannot achieve those goals.

Our government fixes sustainable development goals to achieve in specific time duration and in these various goals are added and we cannot achieve those goals without women empowerment. Women empowerment is necessary for achieving the sustainable development goals. It is also important to increase income equality and economic development of the nation. It also increases women's access to opportunities and resources. To educate women is very important because it is one of the most important ways to empower women. Education provides knowledge, skills, and self-confidence and these skills help in women development.

Challenges and obstacles to women's empowerment in India:

Women face many problems throughout their empowering journey. There are so many practical obstacles to women in general in all institutions to which they are not yet overcome.

Some of them are lack of awareness, knowledge and experience to handle the new challenges in various institutions, and a poor level of literacy is also one of the obstacles in women empowerment.

1. Gender based violence –

Women face various problems throughout their empowerment such as domestic violence, sexual harassment and dowry-related crises. It harms women physically and psychologically and all these factors restrict their freedom and limit their opportunities.

2. Gender pay gap –

Gender pay gap is the major obstacle in women empowerment women cannot get equal pay as men. It impacts on their mental health as well as their economic status. Women should get equal pay wages as men have a gender pay gap.

3. Limited Access to Education-

In Indian society girls get limited access to education because of poverty, cultural norms. Girls get limited access to education mostly girls get only primary education which is provided free of cost by the government. In higher education girls' rate of education is very low. They didn't get good infrastructure and opportunities for education. It restricts women's skills acquisition and economic prospects.

4. Limited Political Representation-

Women have limitations for political representation. Women are generally free from corruption and more responsive to the needs of the community. Worldwide, there is a need for women's education to inbuilt confidence, clarity of purpose, priorities, commitment and the ability to present their case skilfully. The political empowerment of women requires a transformation of existing political structure and systems, rendering them more responsive to women (Walter, p.1)

5. Social Norms and Cultural Barriers-

Indian society has various social norms and cultural rituals and tradition and for women there are so many cultural and tradition rituals in society. Every woman must follow all these and its effect on women empowerment. Our deep-rooted patriarchal norms, gender stereotypes and discriminatory customs all these factors restrict women's autonomy and it affects their opportunities because of all these societal norms women get less opportunities to represent their skills.

Indian government schemes for women empowerment-

There are several schemes run by the Indian government for empowering women. Women are 50% of the population and it is very important to give them opportunities and enhance their knowledge. Empowerment of women emphasizes on creation of an environment which promotes equality between women and men. Indian government policies, planning and schemes tried to create this environment.

Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP)-

Beti Bachao Beti Padhao program addresses the child sex ratio and empowers women throughout their lives. This program supports the girl child education and provides some amount to the girl child's parents to raise them properly and give them access to education. It mainly targets the clusters in north states of India, such as Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, Haryana, Uttarakhand, Bihar and Delhi. There are major reasons for this initiative like sex-selective abortion and its effect on sex ratio.

Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY)-

Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana launched by the government of India to economically support pregnant women. It was previously known as the Indira Gandhi matrutva sahyog yojana and it was renamed in 2017. It is implemented by the Ministry of Women and Child Development. Through this program the government provides cash incentives to pregnant and nursing mothers. Through this scheme pregnant and nursing women get all needed health care facilities as well as healthy food and nutrition supplements from government health care centres.

Swadhar Gruha-

The Swadhar Gruha scheme is launched by the ministry of women and child development to provide support to affected women who are in difficult circumstances

.Through this program the government provides food, shelter, clothing and medical facilities to women. Women who are survivor of natural disaster, women prisoners who released from jail and do not have any social and economic support

get help through these scheme. 18 years old women victims of violence, abuse, face trafficking and widows deserted by their families are eligible for this scheme

Ladki Bahin Yojan-

This scheme was launched by the Chief Minister of Maharashtra State. It provides 1500 rupees per month to women aged 21 to 60 years old. It is very important to empower women economically.

Conclusion:

Women empowerment is very essential in nation building. Women empowerment increases the economic growth of the country. It is important for achieving the sustainable development goals. It is important to political stability and social transformation of the country. The Indian government provides various facilities to women by several government schemes which help them to empower themselves. These all government schemes give economic and mental stability to all women. Mahila samman scheme, Namo Drone Didi, Mission Shakti, Widow home, working women hostel, crèche scheme, Nirbhaya fund

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